

REEVALUATE: Framework for safe, open, collaborative and inclusive digitization and management of cultural heritage

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Abstract

REEVALUATE is a project situated in the Cultural Heritage (CH) domain, aiming to provide an actionable framework consisting of guidelines, recommendations and technical enablers for digitisation of cultural artefacts. Semantic Web technologies will provide the basis for these enablers.

The Cultural Artefact's Contextual Ontology (CACAO) is used as a central data model to integrate data from four CH institutes, operating in different domains with data in a variety of modalities (images, 3D models, audio and textual metadata). This data is stored in a knowledge graph (ARTKB), serving as the central data storage for the project. Different AI-based technological enablers will be created with this data at their core. In addition, the large-scale repository Wikidata is mapped to the ontology and added to the knowledge graph to provide AI models with sufficient data for enhanced performance.

Keywords

Cultural Heritage Digitization, Digital Cultural Heritage, Cultural Heritage Management, Ontology, Knowledge Graph, CIDOC-CRM, ODRL, Intellectual Property Rights, Copyright Management, Collaborative Framework, AI in Cultural Heritage

1. Project information

- Project short name/acronym: REEVALUATE
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- Project logo: https://reevaluate.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/REEVALUATE_Logos.zip
- Project video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XL8L_1MnA88

2. Project summary

The REEVALUATE project aims to enable collaboration, boost creative reuse and promote democratic and inclusive prioritisation and contextualisation. To achieve this, the REEVALUATE project develops a modular framework that facilitates each stage of a digitised artefact’s life cycle (prioritisation, contextualisation, storage, collaboration and reuse) through three *semantic management enablers* and three *collaboration and intellectual property rights enablers*. The *semantic management enablers* include

(i) the **Public Sensing Prioritization enabler** that democratises the prioritisation of the artefacts to be digitised. Social sensing and gamification techniques are considered to automate the prioritisation process. Through their social media profiles, curators or representatives of the hosting institution can create campaigns for different cultural artefacts, through which the public will input their interests.

(ii) the **Semantic Contextualisation enabler** that is responsible for the interpretation, content analysis and understanding of data associated with CH artefacts based on the REEVALUATE ontology.

(iii) the **Human-driven Contextualisation enabler** that allows stakeholders to contribute their views and stories related to cultural assets. Participants provide feedback in the form of text, images or video, and moderators review and manage the contributions, ensuring that the context is appropriate.

The *collaboration and intellectual property rights enablers* include

(iv) the **Collaboration enabler** that empowers the collaboration between CH institutions and third parties interested in the discovery and re-use of digitised assets;

(v) the **Creative Reuse enabler** that produces new content, such as synthetic realistic images based on selected digitised artefacts and prompts provided by users in natural language; and

(vi) the **Context Validation enabler** that identifies and validates the existence of a digitised CH artefact in a desired/undesired reuse context, given a set of appropriate and restricted contexts.

Besides the Public Sensing Prioritization enabler, all the other enablers rely on the REEVALUATE knowledge graph. The REEVALUATE framework comes with a semantic representation of the artefact’s metadata to improve its accessibility and discoverability and enable automated discovery of digitised CH object misuses. To achieve this, the project has created the Cultural Artefacts’ Contextual Ontology (CACAO) as a central data model. CACAO extends CIDOC-CRM [1] with the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) [2], and additional concepts and properties. Cultural Heritage in several formats is translated to RDF and added to the knowledge graph (ARTKB) to serve as a semantic base for the aforementioned enablers.

The REEVALUATE marketplace, i.e. a market place for artefact reuse, includes intelligent search and discoverability features developed in the collaboration enabler. The marketplace provides a user interface for the collection managers to promote artefacts to potential interested parties and forms the primary component that users will interact with. Interested parties can search and discover artefacts to view their contextual information and request their reuse. The marketplace indicates context restrictions for the artefacts, i.e. under what condition an artefact can and cannot be used, and takes care of the price negotiation and the IP rights management agreement for an artefact’s reuse.

The REEVALUATE framework and tools will be validated through three real-world pilot cases across different European regions and Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs), including (1) the Fashion and Gaming industries, (2) the Advertising industry and (3) the Tourism industry.

3. Project available results

The REEVALUATE project comes with relevant contributions for the semantic web community, as the REEVALUATE framework has a knowledge graph at its base and the enablers use semantic web technologies to interact with the knowledge graph. The most relevant contributions include so far:

- A critical review of the benefits, risks, gaps and opportunities in the management of CH digitisation (accepted at EuroMed 2024) and interviews [3].
- the **CACAO ontology**, <http://w3id.org/cacao>
- the **ARTKB knowledge graph**, <https://loki.linksfoundation.com/reevaluate-graphdb/>

The requirements for the Cultural Artefacts' Contextual Ontology (CACAO) were identified through the critical review and interviews, as well as the input from four CH institutes (AQUILEIA, MoMU, OLYMPIC, SMB), ensuring that the ontology is applicable to real-world data and as such usable in practice. In addition, the ontology was designed considering the REEVALUATE project's use-cases, such as providing context to artefacts through AI in multiple modalities, as well as the requirements of the enablers. CACAO extends CIDOC-CRM [1] with the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) [2] to semantically express rights statements for reuse of the artefacts and concepts such as *cacao:Digital Artefact*, *cacao:Physical Artefact* and *cacao:Social Movement* with corresponding properties such as *cacao:movement*.

Using this ontology, the ARTKB knowledge graph was created and is currently being expanded with data from the different CH institutes and interlinked with Wikidata. More specifically, sample data from each of the institutes in different formats (XML, Excel, RDF) were analysed and mapped to CACAO, using RML [4] and other mapping techniques, based on the original data format. The concepts in the ARTKB knowledge graph were also interlinked with concepts in Wikidata (<https://www.wikidata.org/>).

The main contributions of the project are available under <https://reevaluate.eu/deliverables/>.

4. Relevance to ESWC conference

The REEVALUATE project advances the digitization and valorization of cultural heritage by leveraging knowledge representation and semantic web technologies. At the heart of the REEVALUATE framework lies a robust knowledge graph, which serves as the central hub for integrating, structuring, and interlinking heterogeneous cultural heritage data. Various enablers operate on the basis of this knowledge graph, enabling functionalities such as metadata enrichment, provenance tracking, rights management, and intelligent content reuse. Each enabler interacts with and builds upon the shared semantic backbone, demonstrating a highly interoperable, scalable and reusable architecture. Due to its modular design and layered knowledge graph, the REEVALUATE framework not only supports intellectual property (IP) rights management in the cultural heritage sector, but it can also be replicated for other domains. The REEVALUATE framework is particularly relevant in contexts where the reuse of digital assets must be balanced with considerations related to rights management and price negotiation.

5. Value brought by the project to ESWC participants

Attendees can gain knowledge from the project's experiences in integrating real-world cultural heritage data. The project will provide a knowledge graph that integrates this data, offering a practical resource for researchers and developers. Additionally, REEVALUATE offers a practical implementation of CIDOC-CRM, extending it with ways to express rights semantically, using ODRL (Open Digital Rights Language), as well as a taxonomy of the most used rights statements.

The results of the REEVALUATE project are relevant for and can be reused by not only cultural heritage experts, but also the broader semantic web community. The framework, its ontology and its enablers are designed to be domain-agnostic, making them adaptable to other fields where the reuse of digital assets under legal or contextual constraints is a key concern. At the current stage

of the project, a major achievement is the design and demonstration of CACAO, the REEVALUATE ontology, and ARTKB, the REEVALUATE knowledge graph, which serve as the semantic backbone of the REEVALUATE framework. While CACAO is directly applicable to the cultural heritage domain, it also offers broader relevance to semantic web practitioners. Its layered architecture distinguishes between high-level and domain-specific concepts, making the upper levels reusable across various fields. As the design of CACAO enables experts in other domains to adopt and adapt CACAO for their own asset reuse scenarios, where IP rights must be clearly modeled and enforced, makes the ontology and the framework interested in a wider audience. In this way, REEVALUATE and CACAO not only support cultural heritage digitization but also contribute to a generalizable and scalable framework for knowledge representation and digital content governance.

6. Value gained by the project from ESWC participation

The project is actively seeking collaborations with other projects and partners, both within and outside its immediate field, to explore synergies and potential joint initiatives. A key objective of this outreach is to engage with domain experts, practitioners, and researchers in areas such as cultural heritage and digital humanities, intellectual property management and data governance, education, etc. Through these interactions, the REEVALUATE project aims to facilitate meaningful knowledge exchange, gain insight into complementary methodologies, and integrate external expertise that can strengthen and expand the project's impact. The project's technical partners are committed to exploring new application areas for the framework. This includes assessing how the framework, including the ontology, the knowledge graph and the enablers, can be adapted and optimized for use in other sectors where asset reuse, provenance tracking, and rights management are equally critical.

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